

Stages of Embryonic Development of the Axolotl (*Ambystoma mexicanum*).

Yosuke Yamazaki *

Department of Anatomy, Nihon University School of Dentistry

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Introduction

The Mexican axolotl (*Ambystoma mexicanum*) is a salamander of which native habitat is Lake Xochimilco, Mexico. It has been used as a research model. The sequence of its embryonic developmental stage was reported [1,2]. Based on the criteria of staging, external morphological features are shown in picture in this technical note.

Materials and Methods

Animals

Axolotls, *Ambystoma mexicanum*, were kept at 18–20 °C in water and bred in our facility.

Microscopy

A stereomicroscope (MZ FLIII; Leica) with DSFi1C CCD camera (Nikon) was used for observation and recording.

Ethics Statement

This study does not involve human subjects. All procedures were done in amphibian embryos and performed according to local ethics committee guidelines.

Developmental Stages

* yamazai.yosuke@nihon-u.ac.jp
ORCID 0000-0002-5181-8051

Fig.1 Stage 36. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.2 Stage 37. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.3 Stage 38. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.4 Stage 39. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.5 Stage 40. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.6 Stage 41. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.7 Stage 42. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

Fig.8 Stage 43. A; lateral view, B; dorsal view, C; ventral view, D; ventral view (high mag.)

References

- 1 SchreckenberG G (1975) Normal stages of development of the Axolotl, *Ambysoma mexicanum*. *Dev. Biol.* 42: 391–400
- 2 Bordzilovskaya N, Detlaff T and Duhon S (1989) Developmental-stage series of axolotl embryos . In *Developmental Biology of the Axolotl* (pp.201–219). Oxford University press, NY.

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